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SALES AND MARKETING STRATEGY FOR INTERNATIONAL MEDICAL INDUSTRY

Hoe Koon Siong*

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MANAGEMENT OF WORKING CAPITAL IN PUBLIC SECTOR ENTERPRISES: A CASE STUDY OF THE OIL INDIA LTD & CHENNAI PETROLEUM CORP. LTD

Dr. Dharen Kumar Pandey* and Amit Kumar Jaiswal**

ABSTRACT

The main objective of the present study is to examine and evaluate the efficiency of working capital management in OIL and CPCL. It looks into the company's efficiency in the management of the inventories, receivables and cash. To arrive at the conclusion, the current assets, current liabilities and the net working capital during the twelve-year period and various fundamental ratios the effectiveness of working capital management in both the companies have been compared with the help of t-test. This paper not only intends to comprehend the concept of working capital and its management but also to critique various aspects of working capital. With the comparison between two companies from similar industry, the trend most common about working capital management, in this industry and others too, comes out to be bared.

INTRODUCTION

The most common and imperative question that needs to be answered unambiguously and complete in all respect is: What working capital means and what does the management of working capital signify? Working capital refers to that portion of the capital of an organization that is maintained at a specific level to meet its day-to-day expenses. No human body can sustain without appropriate level of blood and so does an organization in the absence of efficient working capital. The working capital consists of three constituents, viz., cash, inventory and receivables. These constituents affect the size of the current assets and the current liabilities, or else, it can be said that these constituents and the current assets and liabilities are interdependent. Conceptualizing the term 'working capital' calls for two concepts- gross working capital and net working capital. Gross working capital refers to all the current assets of the business, while, the net working capital refers to the excess of current assets over current liabilities. Working capital management involves managing tactfully the relationship between a firm's

current assets and its current liabilities. Working capital management may refer to as the managerial efforts in maintaining optimum level of cash, inventory and receivables. The efficient management of working capital is very important from the point of view of both; liquidity and profitability. Poor management of working capital means that funds are unnecessarily clinched up in idle assets, thus, reducing liquidity. A firm can work and survive without making profit but it can't survive without working capital funds. Therefore, proper management of working capital is crucial for the success of the organization. The working capital mix must be appropriate in order to achieve short term liquidity and long term profitability objective of the organization.

Research studies in India have found that many public sector enterprises and their subsidiaries including Bharat Pumps & Compressors Ltd., Eastern Coalfields Ltd., National Thermal Power Corporation, etc have failed to garner the benefits of a proper working capital management. In the present study, a case of a public sector enterprise and one of its subsidiaries has been considered

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for comparison in respect of the efficiency in the management of working capital. Oil India Private Limited, on February 18, 1959, was incorporated to the newly discovered oil fields of Naharkatiya and Moran in the North-Eastern India. In 1981, OIL became a wholly-owned Government of India enterprise. Today, OIL is a premier Indian National Oil Company engaged in the business of exploration, development and production of crude oil and natural gas, transportation of crude oil and production of LPG. CPCL is a group company of the OIL. The main products of the company are LPG, Motor Spirit, Superior Kerosene, Aviation Turbine Fuel, High Speed Diesel, Naphtha, Bitumen, Lube Base Stocks, Paraffin Wax, Fuel Oil, Hexane and Petrochemical feed stocks.

OBJECTIVE, SCOPE & METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the present study is to examine and evaluate the working capital management in OIL and CPCL. It looks into the company's efficiency in the management of the inventories, receivables and cash. The companies have been selected on the basis of their dominance in the field of petroleum. The study is based on secondary data which has been obtained from the published annual reports of OIL and CPCL for a twelve-year period starting from 2003 to 2014. To arrive at the conclusion, the current assets, current liabilities and the net working capital during the twelve-year period have been compared. Thereafter, with the help of various fundamental ratios the effectiveness of working capital management in both the companies has been compared. This paper not only intends to impart the basic knowledge of working capital and its management but also to critique various aspects of working capital. With the comparison between two companies from similar industry, the trend most common about working capital management, in this industry and other, comes out to be bared. T-test has been applied to check whether the management of working capital in the CPCL is like to that in the OIL. The hypothesis for the study is as follows:

H_0 : There is no significant difference between the management of working capital in CPCL and OIL.

H_1 : There is a significant difference between the management of working capital in CPCL and OIL.

LIMITATIONS OF THIS STUDY

This study is fully based on secondary data extracted from the annual reports of these companies as available on their website. Any limitations in the annual reports will add to the limitations of this study. Analysis of the data available is based on ratios, while there other aspects of working capital analysis are not covered. It is a quantitative analysis and the quality aspect of both companies has not been considered.

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

The analysis of working capital management in OIL and CPCL has been done in 2 parts viz; analysis of working capital and the analysis of various ratios. T-values have been calculated to check whether significance differences exist

1. Analysis of Working Capital

The analysis of working capital has been done by analyzing the size of current assets, current liabilities and the net working capital of both the companies. The current assets, current liabilities and net working capital of both the companies have been compared and t values were calculated as depicted in illustrated in a tabular form in Table 1, Table 2 & Table 3. It has been elaborated as below:

• Current Assets

The size of current assets in the OIL has been steady for the period. It increased from Rs.2574.78 crore in 2003 to Rs.15441.84 crore in 2014. Average current assets of the OIL during this period were Rs.9073.47 crore. Current assets in the case of the CPCL showed a fluctuating trend during the period. It declined from Rs.2110.77 crore in 2003 to Rs.2035.74 crore in 2004. Thereafter it increased Rs.3611.71 crore in 2005 and Rs.4605.35 crore in 2006. Next year, it again came down to Rs.4437.88 crore. It again went up to Rs.6155.26 crore in 2008 and down to Rs.9668.97 in the year 2009. There was an increase from Rs.5653.54 crore in the year 2010 to Rs. 7642.78 crore in the year 2011 and even a drastic increase to Rs.10122.17 crore in the year 2012. However, with a mild decrease it rested to Rs.9259.38 crore in the year 2013 and Rs.9188.11 crore in the year 2014. Average current assets of the CPCL for the period were Rs.5707.61 crore.

Table 1: Calculation of t-value for Current assets of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	Current Assets	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$	Current Assets	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$
2003	2574.78	-6498.69	42232971.72	2110.77	-3596.84	12937257.99
2004	2797.88	-6275.59	39383029.85	2035.74	-3671.87	13482629.30
2005	3521.73	-5551.74	30821817.03	3611.71	-2095.90	4392796.81
2006	4555.48	-4517.99	20412233.64	4605.35	-1102.26	1214977.11
2007	5510.67	-3562.80	12693543.84	4437.88	-1269.73	1612214.27
2008	6176.56	-2896.91	8392087.55	6155.26	447.65	200390.52
2009	8355.35	-718.12	515696.33	3668.97	-2038.64	4156053.05
2010	12269.54	3196.07	10214863.44	5653.24	-54.37	2956.10
2011	14801.05	5727.58	32805172.66	7642.78	1935.17	3744882.93
2012	15948.50	6875.03	47266037.50	10122.17	4414.56	19488339.99
2013	16928.30	7854.83	61698354.33	9259.38	3551.77	12615070.13
2014	15441.84	6368.37	40556136.46	9188.11	3480.50	12113880.25
Mean (M)	9073.47		164666243.40	5707.61		37999275.14
t-value				3.61 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)		

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the currents assets of the OIL & the CPCL.

- Current Liabilities

The current liabilities of OIL have been increasing during the period except in the year 2004 and 2007. It went up from Rs.621.20 crore in 2003 to Rs.10581.70 crore in the year 2014. The major increase in the current liabilities of the OIL was notice in the year 2014 when it went up to Rs.10581.70 crore

from Rs.4302.61 crore in the year 2013, i.e., 146 per cent increase. Average current liabilities of OIL for the period were Rs.2871.77 crore. On the other side, the current liabilities of the CPCL have been fluctuating. From Rs.1190 crore in 2003, it came down to Rs.1159.80 crore in 2004. It has been rising for the next four years, but again came down to Rs.2252.68 crore in 2009 and to Rs.1770.61 crore in 2010. But from the year 2011 onwards, it increased to a drastic level marking 90 per cent increase in 2011 and 200 per cent increase in 2012. However, the average current liabilities of the CPCL for the period were Rs.4120.43 crore.

Table 2: Calculation of t-value for Current liabilities of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	Current Liabilities	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$	Current Liabilities	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$
2003	621.20	-2250.57	5065065.32	1190.00	-2930.43	8587419.98
2004	551.24	-2320.53	5384859.48	1159.80	-2960.63	8765330.00
2005	871.96	-1999.81	3999240.04	2089.89	-2030.54	4123092.69
2006	1166.78	-1704.99	2906990.90	2402.62	-1717.81	2950871.20
2007	1032.00	-1839.77	3384753.65	2766.46	-1353.97	1833234.76
2008	1754.06	-1117.71	1249275.64	3088.24	-1032.19	1065416.20
2009	3091.36	219.59	48219.77	2252.68	-1867.75	3488490.06
2010	3269.29	397.52	158022.15	1770.61	-2349.82	5521654.03
2011	3321.61	449.84	202356.03	3388.34	-732.09	535955.77
2012	3897.41	1025.64	1051937.41	9670.10	5549.67	30798837.11
2013	4302.61	1430.84	2047303.11	10191.05	6070.62	36852427.18
2014	10581.70	7709.93	59443020.60	9475.32	5354.89	28674846.91
Mean (M)	2871.77		84941044.10	4120.43		133197575.89
t-value				1.82 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)		

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The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the currents assets of the OIL & the CPCL.

- Working Capital

The net working capital of the OIL has been increasing in every year except in the year 2008. It went up from Rs.1953.58 crore in 2003 to Rs.12625.69 crore in 2013, but drastically fell down to Rs.4860.14 in the year 2014, the average for the whole period being Rs.6201.71 crore. On the contrary, the net

working capital of the CPCL has been fluctuating through the period. From Rs.920.77 crore in 2003 it came down to Rs.875.94 crore in 2004. For the next two year it went up with the next decline to Rs.1671.42 crore in the year 2007. It again went up to Rs.3067.02 crore during 2008, but came down to Rs.1416.29 crore in 2009. It again went up to Rs.3882.63 crore in 2010 and up to Rs. 3978.71 crore in 2011. A mild decrease in the figure is noticed during the year 2012 but again taking up the pace in 2013 but finally resting down to Rs.3344.30 crore in the year 2014. The average working capital of the CPCL for the period was Rs.2508.03 crore.

Table 3: Calculation of t-value for Net working capital of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	NWC	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$	NWC	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$
2003	1953.58	-4248.13	18046608.50	920.77	-1587.26	2519394.31
2004	2246.64	-3955.07	15642578.70	875.94	-1632.09	2663717.77
2005	2649.77	-3551.94	12616277.76	1521.82	-986.21	972610.16
2006	3388.70	-2813.01	7913025.26	2202.73	-305.30	93208.09
2007	4478.67	-1723.04	2968866.84	1671.42	-836.61	699916.29
2008	4422.50	-1779.21	3165588.22	3067.02	558.99	312469.82
2009	5263.99	-937.72	879318.80	1416.29	-1091.74	1191896.23
2010	9000.25	2798.54	7831826.13	3882.63	1374.60	1889525.16
2011	11479.44	5277.73	27854433.95	3978.71	1470.68	2162899.66
2012	12051.09	5849.38	34215246.38	3343.90	835.87	698678.66
2013	12625.69	6423.98	41267519.04	3870.85	1362.82	1857278.35
2014	4860.14	-1341.57	1799810.06	3344.30	836.27	699347.51
Mean (M)	6201.71		174201099.66	2508.03		15760942.01
t-value	4.17 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the currents assets of the OIL & the CPCL.

2. Analysis of Ratio

Ratio analysis has been the most traditional approach to access the performance of working capital in any organization. Various ratios have been calculated with the help of the annual reports of these companies. Table 4 to Table 12 portrays the ratios and t-values of Oil India Ltd and Chennai Petroleum Corp. Ltd. The same has been elaborated below:

- Inventory Turnover Ratio – ITR

Inventory turnover ratio, represented as the ratio of Cost of Goods sold to average inventory, refers to the number of times a company's inventory is sold and replaced over a period. It is considered as the symbol of liquidity. It is considered that higher the ITR, the lesser will be the holding cost. The lesser the holding cost and the higher is the net income and profitability. A low inventory turnover implies poor sales, and therefore, excess inventory than required.

Table 4: Calculation of t-value for Inventory Turnover Ratio of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	ITR (in times)	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$	ITR (in times)	$\Sigma(X- M)$	$\Sigma(X- M)^2$
2003	6.62	-3.30	10.89	6.31	-1.08	1.17
2004	7.05	-2.87	8.24	6.75	-0.64	0.41
2005	8.40	-1.52	2.31	5.49	-1.90	3.61
2006	7.00	-2.92	8.53	6.48	-0.91	0.83
2007	6.87	-3.05	9.30	7.41	0.02	0.00
2008	7.17	-2.75	7.56	5.93	-1.46	2.13
2009	7.49	-2.43	5.90	13.18	5.79	33.52
2010	8.50	-1.42	2.02	5.55	-1.84	3.39
2011	16.21	6.29	39.56	8.03	0.64	0.41
2012	18.49	8.57	73.44	7.91	0.52	0.27
2013	15.44	5.52	30.47	7.35	-0.04	0.00
2014	9.76	-0.16	0.03	8.24	0.85	0.72
Mean (M)	9.92		198.26	7.39		46.46
t-value	1.95 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the inventory turnover ratio of the OIL & the CPCL. However, the average ITR of the OIL has been more than that of CPCL, hence, it can be said that OIL has been successful in maintaining its inventory well as compared to CPCL.

• Inventory Conversion Period – ICP

Inventory conversion period, represented as inventory to cost of goods sold multiplied by 365 days; refer to the average time required to convert the total inventory into sales. The lesser the ICP, the better it is for the company. Lesser conversion period means that the company is able to convert its inventory into cash within better time intervals.

Table 5: Calculation of t-value for Inventory Conversion Period of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	ICP (in days)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	ICP (in times)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	54.46	13.12	172.13	57.07	5.52	30.47
2004	51.03	9.69	93.90	53.33	1.78	3.17
2005	42.82	1.48	2.19	65.62	14.07	197.96
2006	51.34	10.00	100.00	55.56	4.01	16.08
2007	52.44	11.10	123.21	48.60	-2.95	8.70
2008	50.21	8.87	78.68	60.67	9.12	83.17
2009	48.08	6.74	45.43	27.31	-24.24	587.58
2010	42.36	1.02	1.04	64.89	13.34	177.96
2011	22.51	-18.83	354.57	45.43	-6.12	37.45
2012	19.74	-21.60	466.56	46.13	-5.42	29.38
2013	23.64	-17.70	313.29	49.66	-1.89	3.57
2014	37.39	-3.95	15.60	44.28	-7.27	52.85
Mean (M)	41.34		1766.60	51.55		1228.35
t-value	2.44 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the inventory conversion period of the OIL & the CPCL. However, the average ICP of the OIL has been lower than that of the CPCL; hence, the OIL is quicker than CPCL in the process of conversion of inventory to cash.

• Debtor Turnover Ratio – DTR

Debtor turnover ratio, represented as the ratio of total credit sales to average debtors, shows the efficiency in extending credit as well as collecting debts. A high DTR

means that the company is either trading more in cash or its credit extension and debt collection policy is very much efficient. A low DTR would, thus, mean that its credit policy needs to be re-examined. The average debtor turnover of the CPCL has been much more than that of the OIL, thus, it seems that either the CPCL trades more in cash or its credit policy has been much more effective than OIL's.

Table 6: Calculation of t-value for Debtor Turnover Ratio of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	DTR (in times)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	DTR (in days)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	2.95	-9.57	91.58	13.24	-6.97	48.58
2004	5.15	-7.37	54.32	16.55	-3.66	13.40
2005	6.88	-5.64	31.81	15.92	-4.29	18.40
2006	10.24	-2.28	5.20	17.85	-2.36	5.57
2007	12.93	0.41	0.17	24.64	4.43	19.62
2008	9.76	-2.76	7.62	18.55	-1.66	2.76
2009	17.64	5.12	26.21	31.54	11.33	128.37
2010	11.75	-0.77	0.59	29.23	9.02	81.36
2011	32.52	20.00	400.00	19.21	-1.00	1.00
2012	9.38	-3.14	9.86	13.22	-6.99	48.86
2013	11.02	-1.50	2.25	18.37	-1.84	3.39
2014	19.99	7.47	55.80	24.25	4.04	16.32
Mean (M)	12.52		685.41	20.21		387.63
t-value	3.49 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the debtor turnover ratio of the OIL & the CPCL.

• Average Collection Period – ACP

Average collection period, represented as the debtor turnover ratio divided by 365 days, refers to the average time taken to collect trade debts. The higher the collection period, the worse it is for the organization.

Table 7: Calculation of t-value for Average Collection Period of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL		CPCL			
	ACP (in days)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	ACP (in days)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	122.17	80.76	6522.18	27.19	7.94	63.04
2004	69.95	28.54	814.53	21.75	2.50	6.25
2005	52.34	10.93	119.46	22.61	3.36	11.29
2006	35.14	-6.27	39.31	20.16	0.91	0.83

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2007	27.84	-13.57	184.14	14.61	-4.64	21.53
2008	36.87	-4.54	20.61	19.41	0.16	0.03
2009	20.41	-21.00	441.00	11.41	-7.84	61.47
2010	30.65	-10.76	115.78	12.32	-6.93	48.02
2011	11.22	-30.19	911.44	18.99	-0.26	0.07
2012	38.92	-2.49	6.20	27.59	8.34	69.56
2013	33.12	-8.29	68.72	19.87	0.62	0.38
2014	18.26	-23.15	535.92	15.05	-4.20	17.64
Mean (M)	41.41		9779.30	19.25		300.10
t-value	2.89 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the average collection period of the OIL & the CPCL. The average collection period of the OIL was 41.41 days while that of CPCL was just 19.25 days. It implies that the debts of the CPCL are more liquid than that of the OIL.

- Cash Turnover Ratio – CTR

Cash turnover ratio, represented by cost of goods sold to cash, refers to efficiency of the cash cycle of the organization. It indicates the liquidity of the organization. Higher cash turnover is preferable to the lower one. The average cash turnover ratio of the CPCL was appreciating but that of the OIL was severely low.

Table 8: Calculation of t-value for Cash Turnover Ratio of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	CTR (in times)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	CTR (in times)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	0.83	0.25	0.06	132.08	-35.02	1226.40
2004	0.47	-0.11	0.01	93.31	-73.79	5444.96
2005	0.47	-0.11	0.01	215.45	48.35	2337.72
2006	0.38	-0.20	0.04	39.63	-127.47	16248.60
2007	0.32	-0.26	0.07	242.25	75.15	5647.52
2008	0.41	-0.17	0.03	210.51	43.41	1884.43
2009	0.51	-0.07	0.00	233.92	66.82	4464.91
2010	0.38	-0.20	0.04	123.47	-43.63	1903.58
2011	0.69	0.11	0.01	174.12	7.02	49.28
2012	0.90	0.32	0.10	308.35	141.25	19951.56
2013	0.82	0.24	0.06	117.57	-49.53	2453.22
2014	0.82	0.24	0.06	114.5	-52.6	2766.76
Mean (M)	0.58		0.50	167.10		64378.95
t-value	7.54 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance

difference in the average collection period of the OIL & the CPCL.

- Current Ratio – CR

Current ratio, represented as the ratio of current assets to current liabilities, aims to check whether or not the organization has sufficient fund to meet its expenses over the year. The higher the current ratio, the more capable is the company to pay off its debts. A current ratio of 2:1 is appreciative with a measure that lies between 1.5 and 3. The current ratio of the OIL for all the years as well as the average current ratio has been much more than what is need. It implies that the OIL has been holding much more current assets that were required during the period. The current ratio of the CPCL has been below the benchmark of 2:1 but the average current ratio was nearly 2:1. It should also be noted that for all the years, the current ratio of the CPCL was between 1.5 and 3. Hence, the current ratio of the CPCL would said to be much better than that of the OIL. Although the current ratio of the OIL implied that it was more liquid than CPCL, a high current ratio reduces profitability.

Table 9: Calculation of t-value for Current Ratio of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	CR	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	CR	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	4.14	0.27	0.07	1.77	0.04	0.00
2004	5.08	1.21	1.46	1.76	0.03	0.00
2005	4.04	0.17	0.03	1.73	0.00	0.00
2006	3.90	0.03	0.00	1.92	0.19	0.04
2007	5.34	1.47	2.16	1.60	-0.13	0.02
2008	3.52	-0.35	0.12	2.00	0.27	0.07
2009	2.70	-1.17	1.37	1.63	-0.10	0.01
2010	3.75	-0.12	0.01	3.19	1.46	2.13
2011	4.46	0.59	0.35	2.26	0.53	0.28
2012	4.09	0.22	0.05	1.05	-0.68	0.46
2013	3.93	0.06	0.00	0.91	-0.82	0.67
2014	1.46	-2.41	5.81	0.97	-0.76	0.58
Mean (M)	3.87		11.44	1.73		4.26
t-value	6.97 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the current ratio of the OIL & the CPCL.

- Quick Ratio – QR

Quick ratio, represented as the ratio of quick/near-cash assets to current liabilities, implies the ability of the organization to use its near cash assets to meet out its current

liabilities immediately. A standard quick ratio must be 1:1. The average quick ratio of the OIL was 3.7 and that of the CPCL was 0.6. When compared to the benchmark, none of these companies have satisfactory quick ratio. For an instance, the quick ratio of the OIL directs towards its liquidity, but this liquidity costs a lot in the long run. Hence, none of these companies were efficient enough to maintain the required quick ratio.

Table 10: Calculation of t-value for Quick Ratio of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	QR	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	QR	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	3.78	0.17	0.03	0.76	0.21	0.04
2004	4.67	1.06	1.12	0.71	0.16	0.03
2005	3.74	0.13	0.02	0.57	0.02	0.00
2006	3.56	-0.05	0.00	0.61	0.06	0.00
2007	4.94	1.33	1.77	0.44	-0.11	0.01
2008	3.06	-0.55	0.30	0.56	0.01	0.00
2009	2.54	-1.07	1.14	0.53	-0.02	0.00
2010	3.61	0.00	0.00	0.72	0.17	0.03
2011	4.31	0.70	0.49	0.75	0.20	0.04
2012	3.96	0.35	0.12	0.39	-0.16	0.03
2013	3.78	0.17	0.03	0.28	-0.27	0.07
2014	1.37	-2.24	5.02	0.26	-0.29	0.08
Mean (M)	3.61		10.05	0.55		0.34
t-value	11.82 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference in the quick ratio of the OIL & the CPCL.

• Working Capital Turnover Ratio – WCTR

Working capital turnover ratio, represented by sales to net working capital, refers to the capacity of the organization to generate sales at the cost of working capital. The higher the working capital turnover, the better it is. The working capital of the OIL has not been able to generate enough sales as compared to that of the CPCL. The average WCTR of the OIL was just 1.24 as compared to 11.82 of the CPCL. Hence, the working capital of CPCL was more efficient than that of the OIL.

Table 11: Calculation of t-value for Working Capital Turnover Ratio of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL		CPCL			
	WCTR (in times)	$\Sigma(X-M)$ (in times)	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	WCTR	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	1.45	0.21	0.04	8.77	-3.05	9.30
2004	1.35	0.11	0.01	9.92	-1.90	3.61

2005	1.44	0.20	0.04	9.32	-2.50	6.25
2006	1.61	0.37	0.14	9.60	-2.22	4.93
2007	1.18	-0.06	0.00	14.77	2.95	8.70
2008	1.35	0.11	0.01	9.14	-2.68	7.18
2009	1.36	0.12	0.01	22.57	10.75	115.56
2010	0.86	-0.38	0.14	6.43	-5.39	29.05
2011	0.71	-0.53	0.28	9.58	-2.24	5.02
2012	0.82	-0.42	0.18	13.57	1.75	3.06
2013	0.79	-0.45	0.20	12.10	0.28	0.08
2014	1.98	0.74	0.55	16.12	4.30	18.49
Mean (M)	1.24		1.62	11.82		211.24
t-value	8.50 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference between the working capital turnover ratio of the OIL & the CPCL.

• Return on Total Assets - ROTA

Return on total assets, represented by EBIT to net assets, indicates how effectively a company is using its assets to generate earnings before interest and tax. The greater the return on total assets, the more efficient the company has been in using its assets in generating profits. The average return on total assets of the OIL was 24.44 and that of the CPCL was 7.44. Hence, the OIL has managed its assets more effectively and efficiently than the CPCL.

Table 12: Calculation of t-value for Return on Total Assets of OIL & CPCL

Year	OIL			CPCL		
	ROTA (in %)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$	ROTA (in %)	$\Sigma(X-M)$	$\Sigma(X-M)^2$
2003	24.2	-0.24	0.06	12.56	5.12	26.21
2004	29.61	5.17	26.73	11.29	3.85	14.82
2005	24.67	0.23	0.05	15.48	8.04	64.64
2006	33.42	8.98	80.64	11.22	3.78	14.29
2007	26.28	1.84	3.39	13.69	6.25	39.06
2008	25.61	1.17	1.37	19.94	12.5	156.25
2009	25.38	0.94	0.88	-5.07	-12.51	156.50
2010	21.55	-2.89	8.35	8.34	0.9	0.81
2011	26.65	2.21	4.88	8.33	0.89	0.79
2012	22.13	-2.31	5.34	0.61	-6.83	46.65
2013	20.99	-3.45	11.90	-8.78	-16.22	263.09
2014	12.84	-11.6	134.56	1.71	-22.73	516.65
Mean (M)	24.44		92.59	7.44		375.24
t-value	7.48 (Calculated t-value > Tabulated t-value)					

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The calculated t-value is more than the tabulated t-value at 5 % significance level. Hence, there exists a significance difference between the Return on Total Assets of the OIL & the CPCL.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis of the working capital was successful in attaining the object of the paper and giving vivid suggestions for improvement. The average current assets of the OIL have been more than that of the CPCL. But its average current liabilities have been less than CPCL's. Hence, the average net working capital of the OIL has been much more than that of the CPCL. A current asset equal to more than thrice the current liability indicates that the OIL has been holding excess idle cash. This also indicates that the OIL has not been efficient in managing its working capital as compared to the CPCL. The ratio analysis revealed that although the OIL was better than CPCL in converting its inventory into sales, its credit policies, and the cash turnover ratio has been poor. The current ratio of OIL, although more than that of the CPL, was much above the benchmark. Hence, the OIL has failed to manage its current assets properly. In case of the quick ratio, the benchmark was not met by any of these companies. OIL's quick ratio was much above 1 while CPCL's was below 1. Working capital turnover ratio of CPCL was better than that of the OIL. Huge amount of working capital leads to a poor working capital turnover. OIL should better reduce its current assets. Hence, it can be said that the working capital management of the CPCL had been more efficient than that of the OIL. As far as profits are concerned, the OIL has managed its assets well and CPCL's return on total assets was also good, although not better than that of the OIL. Current Assets, Current Liabilities, and Net Working Capital may vary due to the size of the firm and its internal process (length of manufacturing process). But as far as ratios are concerned, the result of the t-test depicts that there was a significant difference between the management of working capital of both companies because the null hypothesis is rejected in all cases.

Towards home, it is allusive to the management of both these companies to look into the working capital as one of the most important aspects for short term liquidity and long term profitability. The management of the OIL should try to increase its collection efforts. It has excessive investment in the working capital because of large amount of current assets. Hence, it should attempt to lower down its current assets level in order to improve the profitability

and to come in tie with the required yardstick. Higher quick ratio reminds of excess idle cash in OIL. It should better invest the excess cash in some profitable ventures maintaining the optimum level of cash. The management of the CPCL should try to increase the efforts for improving inventory turnover. It should focus at enhancing its sales. The lower quick ratio reveals that it had kept very little amount in the form of cash which has affected its liquidity position. Therefore, it should try to maintain an optimum level of cash.

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